

Concept, Legal Signs and Subject of Gift Contract and its Different Aspects from Charity

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Abstract: This article analyzes the concept, essence, legal signs, subject of the gift contract according to the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its different aspects from the gift. Also, foreign experiences related to this type of contract were studied.

Key points: Will, certificate of inheritance, real estate, donor and recipient, cadastral documents, public security, heir, donation, free transfer of property, official gift, punishment, compulsory community service, correctional work.

There is a saying that there is no big or small gift. But officially, from the point of view of the law, there are also such gifts that are not enough just to receive them with sincerity and thanks. It is necessary to conclude a special contract with the participation of notary offices in the presentation of such gifts. This is a gift contract. According to Article 502 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a gift contract is defined as the free ownership of an object, the transfer of ownership rights, or the assumption of these obligations. The gift contract must clearly indicate the person and the thing to be given. A contract providing for transfer after the death of the donor is not considered valid. Because this is not a gift, it is a testament. The property provided for in the gift contract comes into force from the date of signing the contract by the parties.

The person who made the will is considered the real owner of his property until his death and can cancel, change or supplement it at any time. A gift contract, as soon as it is signed, becomes the property of the other party, and the decision cannot be changed.

If the person intending to make a gift dies before the contract is signed, the future owner of the gift does not have the right to claim the property. This is just a promise. If the work has been started in the notary office and efforts to conclude a contract have been made, the relatives of the deceased can continue the work by issuing the inheritance certificate.

Some people believe that it is impossible to conclude a gift contract with other things, as there are many cases of gifting of real estate, in particular, a house, based on the contract. In fact, an official gift can be a car, a valuable paper, an expensive item, or a large amount of money. The law stipulates as a mandatory condition that notarial approval is required when donating real estate and motor vehicles. In addition to the contracts of this category, the parties can mutually agree or notarize any type of contract depending on their wishes.

A gift contract belongs to the category of contracts that provide for the transfer of ownership rights to the object specified in the contract from one person to another. A gift contract is concluded free of charge, if a certain benefit or benefit is expected from the gift contract, this contract is not registered as a gift contract. In addition, such a contract is not recognized as a gift when the object or right is given as an alternative, or if there is an alternative obligation, and the norms of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on invalidity of the contract are applied to such contracts.

In the gift contract, the object of the gift must be specified. A promise to give a thing or property right to a person for free or to release a person from a property obligation (promise to give a gift), if

the promise is given in the appropriate form and in the future a certain person will be given a thing or property right It is recognized as a gift contract if the purpose of free giving or freeing him from property obligations is clearly visible.

To give an object or property rights to any person for free ora promise to release a person from a property obligation (promise to give a gift), if the promise is made in the appropriate form and the purpose is to give a thing or property right to a specific person for free in the future or to release him from a property obligation is recognized as a gift contract.

The norms of the current Civil Code set a number of requirements for the form of a gift contract. For example, some gift contracts can be made verbally. But the contract of donation of movable property:

- ✓ when the donor is a legal entity;
- ✓ when a contract is concluded between citizens for an amount more than ten times the amount of the basic calculation;
- ✓ in cases where a future gift is promised in the contract, it should be made in a simple written form.

That is, the oral construction of such contracts causes it to be considered invalid. It should not be forgotten that the violation of the requirements of the legal documents related to the gift contract renders the gift contract invalid.

Gift transfer is carried out by presenting it, symbolic transfer (presentation of keys, etc.) or presentation of documents defining the right. Giving a gift, as well as handing over a gift to the recipient, can be done verbally. The real estate donation contract, when the donor is a legal entity, when a contract is concluded between citizens for an amount more than ten times the amount of the basic calculation, in cases where the contract promises future donation, it should be concluded in a simple written form. If the gift contract is registered, the refusal to accept the gift must also be registered with the state.

2. Parties participating in the contract, their rights and obligations

Individuals, legal entities and the state can participate in the gift contract as parties. In the gift contract, the parties must be named as the donor and recipient and have legal capacity.

Gift contracts must be signed by incompetent persons through their guardians. As an exception, we can say that according to Article 29 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, minors between the ages of fourteen and eighteen can be independent receivers and givers of gifts and sign a gift contract. can build based on their salary and stipend. But they do not have the right to dispose of the objects that belong to them on the basis of property rights. In order for such transactions to be performed by minors, the consent of their legal representatives is required. Article 505 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan contains limitations for concluding a gift contract.

According to the civil legislation, there is no restriction on the conclusion of a gift contract between a couple. The donated property belongs only to that person, and it is allowed to collect a fee from it or to appropriate it in another way only with the consent of the owner.

A gift contract may be void if the following circumstances are noted:

1. The gift contract is canceled if both parties agree to it.
2. In cases where the recipient of the gift commits a deliberate crime against the life or health of the donor, his family members or close relatives, it is allowed to cancel the gift in court.
3. In the event that the recipient of the gift intentionally kills the donor, the heirs of the donor have the right to demand the annulment of the gift in court. If the gift receiver's handling of the gift item, which has a great immovable value for the giver, risks its complete disappearance, the giver has the right to demand the annulment of the gift in a court of law.

In the gift contract, the right of the donor to cancel the gift may be stipulated if the recipient dies before the donor. In case of cancellation of the gift, the recipient of the gift must return the gifted item, if it was preserved in its original condition at the time of cancellation of the gift. The rules on refusal to perform a gift contract and cancellation of a gift do not apply to gift contracts concluded orally. By law, weapons or similar items that pose a threat to public safety cannot be donated. The donor has the right to live in the donated apartment as a family member. The donor does not have the right to demand anything in return for the gift.

The main difference between a gift contract and a will is that a contract providing for the transfer of a gift to the recipient after the death of the donor is not recognized in civil law. In such a case, the provisions of the will apply to the gift. Another major difference between a gift and a will is that the property is transferred during the lifetime of the donor.

3. Donation

Donation is a form of gift contract, in which the donation will be directed to public purposes. According to Article 511 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, donations to citizens, treatment, education, social protection institutions and other similar institutions, charitable, scientific and educational institutions, foundations, museums and other cultural institutions, public associations and religious organizations, as well as the state and other subjects of civil law. The donated property will be included in the funds of the person who received it in the future, and will be transferred to his operative management.

The subject of the donation is objects in civil circulation, securities, assets, materials, buildings, structures (one of them part).

To accept a donation permission or consent of someone (i.e. a third party) is not required. No one's permission or consent is required to accept a donation. When a donor donates property to a citizen, he must stipulate the use of this property for a certain purpose, and when donating to legal entities, he can set this condition. In the absence of such a condition, donating property to a citizen is considered a simple gift, and in other cases, the recipient of the gift uses the donated property in accordance with his duties.

A legal entity receiving a donation intended for use for a specific purpose must keep a separate list of operations performed on the use of the donated property.

If it becomes impossible to use the donated property for the purpose indicated by the donor due to a change in the situation, for a purpose other than the property, only with the consent of the donor, if the citizen who donated the property died or if the legal entity that donated the property is reorganized or dissolved — it can be used according to the court decision.

Use of the donated property contrary to the purpose specified by the donor entitles the donor, his heirs or other legal heirs to demand cancellation of the donation.

Internet resources:

1. www.lex.uz.
2. www.legalcity.uz
3. www.constitution.uz.
4. www.pravacheloveka.uz.
5. www.norma.uz.
6. www.advice.uz.